

SCHOOL OF NURSING GRADUATION PROJECT (SoN GP)

SYNOPSIS

Spring Semester
2023-2024

Foreword

It is with great pride that we present the **School of Nursing Graduation Project (SoN GP) Synopses** for Spring Semester 2023-2024, a remarkable collection of research endeavors showcasing the creativity, dedication, and intellectual curiosity of our undergraduate nursing students. This compilation highlights diverse topics in nursing and health, reflecting the students' commitment to addressing contemporary challenges in healthcare. Under the expert guidance of our faculty, these projects exemplify the integration of research and evidence-based practice, key skills essential for professional success. The Graduation Project course is designed to cultivate critical thinking, foster innovation, and prepare our students to excel in the dynamic and demanding healthcare environment.

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES OF NEEDLE STICK INJURY AMONG NURSING STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Althuraya Alaabed Said Alnoufli Fatma Ali Saif Alnadabi
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Nawal Al Abri
Problem Statement	Needle stick injuries (NSIs) are a significant occupational hazard for nursing students, posing a risk for bloodborne infections. This study aims to comprehensively investigate the prevalence, risk factors, and impacts of NSIs among nursing students at the University of Nizwa (UoN).
Significance of the Study	The study offers several benefits for various stakeholders. For universities, it can lead to improved safety protocols, enhanced student education, and a stronger reputation. For the Ministry of Health, the findings can inform policy development, resource allocation, and improved patient safety. For students, the study can enhance safety, increase awareness, and improve career prospects. Additionally, the study can advance research, inform future studies, and promote evidence-based practices in healthcare.
Aim of the Study	to assess the knowledge and practices of needle stick injuries among nursing students at University of Nizwa.
Methodology	A quantitative research design employing a self-constructed questionnaire was used among 159 nursing students using total sampling technique.
Overall Outcome	The needle stick injuries (NSIs) are prevalent among nursing students, with 12% of the participants experiencing an NSI during their clinical training. The majority (77%) of these students reported a single incident, while 23% encountered multiple injuries. A significant portion of the injuries (62%) occurred during needle recapping; a procedure widely recognized as hazardous. Despite extensive training, improper needle recapping remains a critical issue, highlighting the need for improved protocols.
Keywords	<i>knowledge, practice needle stick injuries, nursing students</i>

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GP Title	EVATUATING NURSES PERCEPTIONS OF PATIENT SAFETY CULTURE IN IBRI, OMAN
GP Student(s)	Anwaar Humaid Said Al Saaidi
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Pelagia Paastor de Polonia
Problem Statement	It is consistent with Oman Vision 2040, which aims to provide high-quality, safe healthcare as part of the country's long-term strategy (Oman Vision 2040, 2020). It focuses on raising the bar and increasing the effectiveness of healthcare throughout Oman. Oman's Ministry of Health has made significant efforts to help PSC achieve these goals. According to recent research, organizational learning and cooperation are on the rise, but challenges persist, particularly with staffing, workload, and error reporting (Alshammari et al., 2021). To meet Oman Vision 2040's objectives and give every patient the best possible treatment that is safe and of high quality, it is essential to mitigate these difficulties.
Significance of the Study	Understanding the correlation between job satisfaction (JS) and turnover intention (TI) is essential for healthcare organizations to enhance nurse retention and mitigate the adverse effects of turnover. This study offers actionable insights to improve nursing staff morale, productivity, and overall satisfaction, ultimately elevating patient care and organizational outcomes.
Aim of the Study	The purpose of this study is to assess nurses' perceptions of the patient safety culture at Oman's Ibri Hospital and identify the variables that affect these perceptions. Based on the findings, recommendations will be made to improve the hospital's patient safety culture.
Methodology	A cross-sectional, quantitative study was carried out using the Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture (HSOPSC), a validated tool for assessing PSC in healthcare settings. A stratified random sample of 100 registered nurses across various departments at Ibri Hospital participated in the study.
Overall Outcome	The findings revealed a generally positive perception of patient safety culture, with high scores for teamwork within units (M = 4.10) and communication practices (M = 4.22). However, areas for improvement were identified, particularly in terms of workload management (M = 3.03) and the promotion of a non-punitive reporting culture (M = 3.61). The questionnaire's overall reliability was high (Cronbach's alpha = 0.975), indicating that the tool was internally consistent.
Keywords	<i>nurses' perceptions, patient safety culture, healthcare quality, communication openness, staffing, Oman, Ibri Hospital</i>

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GP Title	ASSESS KNOWLEDGE, AND COMPLIANCE WITH STANDARD PRECAUTIONS FOR INFECTION CONTROL AMONG NURSING STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Bara'ah Saleem Salim Al Batrani
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Jaha Anand
Problem Statement	Communicable and infectious diseases are still existed in hospitals in Oman especially in critical areas and medical wards. If standard precautions compliance is not observed, it will lead to more increasing in healthcare associated diseases which will increase cost, care, and hospital burdens.
Significance of the Study	This research will address the issue nursing students' inadequate understanding, unfavorable perceptions, and subpar practices which evidenced by the prevalence of healthcare associated Communicable and infectious diseases in Oman hospitals. It will help to improve nursing students' practices to be more competent in the clinical areas and will reduce HAIs in the hospitals and the burdens associated.
Aim of the Study	The aim of the study is to identify nursing students' knowledge, and compliance to standard precautions of infection control.
Methodology	A cross sectional study design was followed. Self-administered questionnaire was used as a tool and collected by single contact period among 175 all levels of nursing students and excluded 1st year, Fundamentals of nursing students, and bridging students. A convenience sampling method was used. Burns and Grove (2011), data analysis is a method utilized and Data statistically assessed using a statistical program (SPSS version 20).
Overall Outcome	This study revealed that nursing students of University of Nizwa has a satisfactory level of knowledge (80.51%) on standard precautions, and have suboptimal compliance to SPs practices (51.79%) (n= 3.1).
Keywords	<i>practice, standard precautions, infection control, hospital acquired infections, compliance, communicable diseases</i>

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GP Title	KNOWLEDGE OF META COGNITION AND IT'S EFFECT ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA STUDENTS
GP Student(s)	Nasra Nasser Salim Alsalmi Yaqeen Jaber Hamed Almamari
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Karen Mae Mallillin
Problem Statement	Metacognition, defined as the awareness and regulation of one's own cognitive processes, is a vital skill that influences students' ability to learn effectively and achieve academic success. Despite its recognized importance, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the extent of metacognitive knowledge among students at the University of Nizwa and how this knowledge affects their academic performance.
Significance of the Study	The significance of this study lies in its potential to enhance educational practices and student support at the University of Nizwa by shedding light on the relationship between students' awareness of their metacognition and their academic performance.
Aim of the Study	This study aims to explore the level of knowledge about metacognition among University of Nizwa students and investigate its effect on their academic performance.
Methodology	A cross-sectional design was employed, targeting 100 students. Included in this study are students from different academic years from university of Nizwa and from any major and academic year. Convenience sampling yielded 100 participants, with data collected via an online survey.
Overall Outcome	Results revealed that there is a liner positive relationship between metacognition awareness (MAI score) and academic achievement.
Keywords	<i>metacognition, academic achievement, metacognitive awareness inventory (MAI)</i>

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GP Title	ASSOCIATION OF LEARNING STYLES AND NURSING STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY COURSE AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Rayan Saleh Al-Rumaidhi
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Dulce Racquel M. Javier
Problem Statement	Bioscience courses, particularly Anatomy and Physiology (A&P), are fundamental to nursing education, serving as prerequisites for advanced nursing coursework and clinical practice. Inadequate understanding of A&P can adversely affect clinical outcomes and increase the likelihood of errors in nursing practice. Additionally, learning styles—individual preferences for processing and retaining information—significantly influence educational success.
Significance of the Study	For nurses to provide patients with high-quality care and optimal patient outcomes, better understanding in human biosciences is essential. Thus, nursing students should be aware of their learning styles to help themselves learn in a better and more efficient way. Instructors should also be aware of students' learning styles to guide students with better knowledge acquisition and retention of content.
Aim of the Study	The study aimed to investigate the relationship between nursing students' learning styles and their academic performance in A&P courses and to validate how learning preferences impact educational achievements in this critical area.
Methodology	The study utilized a quantitative descriptive correlational design. An online survey utilizing Google Forms with a self-administered questionnaire was employed and distributed to 112 nursing students who had completed both A&P courses. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 24 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	Result showed that the students predominantly prefer Auditory learning, with a mean score of 5.35, followed by Visual learning (mean score = 4.16). Read/Write is the least preferred (mean score = 1.94), and Kinesthetic learning has a moderate preference (mean score = 3.55). There is a significant relationship between learning styles and performance in Anatomy and Physiology courses. Auditory learning positively correlates with higher grades in both Anatomy & Physiology I ($r = 0.420$, $p = 0.000$) and II ($r = 0.366$, $p = 0.000$). In contrast, Visual learning negatively correlates with performance in both courses (Anatomy & Physiology I: $r = -0.299$, $p = 0.001$; Anatomy & Physiology II: $r = -0.237$, $p = 0.012$). No significant correlations were found for Read/Write or Kinesthetic learning styles. However, age, academic level, and degree do not significantly affect performance.
Keywords	<i>Anatomy and Physiology (A&P), academic performance, learning style, University of Nizwa</i>

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GP Title	CHILDHOOD OBESITY AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG GIRLS IN GRADE 5-12 IN AL-SHARQIYAH AND AL-BATINAH GOVERNORATE
GP Student(s)	Shiam Ahmed Nabhan Almamari Shahad Hilal Ali Alrawahi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Children who are overweight or obese have a higher chance of developing non-communicable illnesses earlier in life, as well as a higher likelihood of being fat until adulthood. There is limited research about childhood obesity in both Al-Sharqiyah and Al-Batinah Wilayat.
Significance of the Study	The conduct of this study on the factors of obesity for children from grades 5-12 is significant because it will help understand the reasons behind this problem and develop preventive programs.
Aim of the Study	The aim of this study was to explore childhood obesity and associated factors among girls in grade 5-12 in the Al Sharqiyah and Al Batinah governorates.
Methodology	The study sample consists of 2 classes of students from each school who wish to participate, a cross-sectional population-based study measured the weight, height, and BMI of healthy asymptomatic school-aged Omani children from grade 5-12 only girls, attending Al-Thabiti school in Sharqiyah and Um Habiba school (9-12) in Almusanaa.
Overall Outcome	Analysis of dietary and health indicators associated with obesity among children in the Al Sharqiya and Al Batinah revealed several important insights. There was no significant difference in the number of main meals per day between the two regions, indicating that meal frequency in itself does not determine obesity in children. Physical activity data did not show any significant differences, suggesting that general environmental conditions may play a greater role in influencing children's activity levels than direct dietary factors. Policymakers should consider legislation to support healthy eating environments in schools and communities and ensure that all children have access to nutritious food and opportunities for physical activity.
Keywords	<i>obesity, childhood obesity, school girls, body mass index</i>

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GP Title	ASSESS THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF NURSING STUDENTS OF UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA REGARDING DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN HEALTHCARE SYSTEM
GP Student(s)	Almazoon Al Hosni Alanood Saleem Al Dhari
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Karen Mae Mallillin
Problem Statement	As healthcare systems worldwide undergo significant digital transformation, the integration of technologies such as electronic health records, telehealth services, artificial intelligence, and mobile health applications is becoming more prevalent.
Significance of the Study	The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the improvement of nursing education and healthcare practice in a rapidly evolving digital landscape. As digital transformation increasingly shapes healthcare systems worldwide, future nursing professionals must be adequately prepared to engage with and utilize these technologies effectively.
Aim of the Study	This study aims to assess the knowledge and attitudes of nursing students at the University of Nizwa regarding digital transformation in healthcare systems.
Methodology	A cross-sectional survey was conducted among nursing students from various academic years. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data on students' knowledge of digital healthcare concepts, their attitudes toward the use of digital tools, and perceived challenges or benefits associated with digital transformation. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to assess the overall preparedness of the students.
Overall Outcome	Many students expressed positive attitudes toward digital transformation but also highlighted challenges such as adapting to new systems and concerns about data privacy and security.
Keywords	<i>digital transformation, electrical health record, mobile health</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CARING FOR OLDER PERSONS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA, OMAN
GP Student(s)	Alaa Sulaiman Al Wahaibi Hanna Sulaiyam Al Jassasi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Nursing students' apathy for interacting with older adults, despite their basic knowledge, is a worrying trend in many nursing schools. Studies have reported that provision of quality health services to older persons rely strongly on health workers' attitudes towards them. Among students, one of the barriers to this provision of quality health care to older persons comes from negative attitudes, which have a negative consequence on healthcare outcomes.
Significance of the Study	Assessing attitude of nursing students towards caring for older persons is important in improving the quality of care provided for elderly clients during their clinical placement and when they care for the elderly in their future roles as professional nurses.
Aim of the Study	The study assessed the attitude of undergraduate nursing students towards caring for older adults and determined any significant differences based on sociodemographic characteristics.
Methodology	A quantitative cross-sectional study was conducted at the University of Nizwa, Oman. Data were collected from 153 undergraduate nursing students who completed a self-administered questionnaire that included the Geriatric Attitudes Scale (Reuben et al., 1998), which has a reportedly high validity and reliability.
Overall Outcome	The overall mean attitude score was $M=3.11$, indicating a neutral attitude toward caring for older adults. No statistically significant difference in mean attitude score based on sociodemographic characteristics was observed. Addressing this neutral attitude through comprehensive modules on gerontological nursing that go beyond theory should be given top priority in nursing education programs and contribute to the development of a more compassionate approach to caring for older individuals.
Keywords	<i>geriatric attitude, undergraduate nursing students, attitude towards older persons, care of older persons</i>

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GP Title	ASSESSMENT OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE PATTERNS OF MALE ADULTS ATTENDING FITNESS CENTERS IN AD-DAKHLYAH, OMAN
GP Student(s)	Dawood Hamed AL-Battashi Faisal Abdullah Ali AL-Hinai
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Lifestyle pattern is considered by health experts to be one of the most important factors influencing our health. Studies have shown that membership in fitness centers is linked with improved health responsibility and health promoting lifestyles. In Oman, no research activity has been reported about the healthy lifestyle pattern among attendees of fitness clubs or fitness centers.
Significance of the Study	The impact of attending a "Fitness Center" along with a "healthy lifestyle" can be effective for the improvement of the health situation of the targeted population in Oman. Thus, this research will share information among adults in Oman related to the health benefits of attending "Fitness Centers".
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to assess the healthy lifestyle patterns among male adults who are attending fitness centers in select municipalities of Ad Dakhiliyah Governorate, Oman.
Methodology	The study is quantitative descriptive, cross-sectional survey using convenience sample of 92 male adults attending fitness centers in 5 different municipalities of Ad Dakhiliyah region, Oman. Data collection was done using a survey questionnaire with items on demographic profile and the Health style: A Self-Test (Bobroff, 2015). Ethical approval to conduct the study was obtained through the Office of Research and Graduate Studies of the College of Health Sciences of the University of Nizwa.
Overall Outcome	Overall, healthy lifestyle patterns for the male adults attending fitness centers in 5 municipalities of Ad Dakhiliyah region of Oman indicated good health practices. A statistically significant difference in healthy lifestyle pattern in the area of exercise and fitness between regular and non-regular members was found ($p < .05$), that fitness center regular membership is related to healthy lifestyle behaviors of exercise/fitness.
Keywords	<i>healthy lifestyle, fitness center membership, healthstyle patterns, male adults, Ad Dakhiliyah, Oman</i>

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GP Title	AUTISM KNOWLEDGE AND STIGMA AMONG TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Dhikra Abdullah Salim AlRiyami Maryam Hadid AlBriki
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Oman's autism prevalence is expected to rise to 0.2% in 2024. Raising public awareness and informing future teachers about the autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is crucial to help autistic children develop skills and prevent stigma.
Significance of the Study	The study will increase the community awareness especially among teacher education students about the abilities and talents of autistic individuals to establish an inclusive community that provide equal opportunities for all.
Aim of the Study	The study aimed to assess the knowledge and stigma of autism among teacher education students at the University of Nizwa.
Methodology	The study is a descriptive survey on the knowledge and stigma about autism spectrum disorder among 199 teacher education students of University of Nizwa. Data was collected using Autism Stigma and Knowledge Questionnaire (Harrison et al., 2017). Mean and standard deviation were computed to analyze the level of Autism Knowledge and Stigma. A Kruskal-Wallis H test determine significant differences in the level of Autism Knowledge and Stigma among participants when grouped according to demographic profile.
Overall Outcome	Overall, the participants reported adequate knowledge about autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Specifically, they have adequate knowledge on Diagnosis and Treatment of Autism, however reported inadequate knowledge on Etiology of Autism. In general, the participants did not endorse stigma about autism. There was a statistically significant difference in the level of Knowledge on Treatment of Autism among the participants when grouped according to year of study ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that more comprehensive programs on ASD be offered to the teacher education students, focusing more on the etiology of autism.
Keywords	<i>autism, autism spectrum disorder, knowledge, stigma, teacher education students</i>

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GP Title	ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND BARRIERS ENCOUNTERED BY STAFF NURSES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ASEPTIC TECHNIQUES IN SOHAR HOSPITAL, OMAN
GP Student(s)	Miaad Saif Said AL Shidi Nufa Tisir Mabrook AL Kharusi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Aseptic technique is a critical practice in healthcare aimed at preventing the transmission of microorganisms during medical procedures, thereby reducing the risk of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs). However, adherence to aseptic principles among nursing staff is often suboptimal, posing significant risks to patient safety.
Significance of the Study	This study addresses a critical aspect of patient safety by evaluating the knowledge and identifying the barriers in adhering to aseptic principles and hopefully lead to enhancing compliance thereby reducing infection rates and improving patient outcomes.
Aim of the Study	The main purpose of this study was to determine knowledge and identify barriers faced by nursing staff in implementing aseptic techniques among staff nurses in Sohar hospital.
Methodology	The study followed a quantitative, descriptive, cross-sectional design involving nursing staff employed at Sohar Hospital as participants. Data was collected using a self-administered survey adopted from a free access research literature (Jarelnape, 2023) that was created in accordance with recommendations and pertinent literature that were derived from earlier research on aseptic procedures (Sands, 2023; Lin et al., 2019).
Overall Outcome	Overall, the results show that participants' knowledge of aseptic techniques is relatively high but varies across the group. Most commonly agreed-upon barriers include time constraints and competing priorities, inadequate communication and coordination among healthcare team members, limited support from organizational leadership and lack of adequate training and education. Significant differences in knowledge were observed based on gender, age, education and experience ($p = 0.012$).
Keywords	<i>aseptic technique, healthcare-associated infections, nursing staff, adherence, patient safety, infection control, Sohar Hospital</i>

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GP Title	KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, PRACTICES AND EDUCATIONAL NEEDS TOWARD HEPATITIS C VIRAL INFECTION AMONG OMANI CITIZENS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Zahra Hamood Hamed AL-Aamri Mariya Mubarak AL-Sayghi
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Jaha Anand
Problem Statement	Hepatitis C Viral (HCV) infection remains a significant public health concern. Even while a persistent HCV infection may go undiagnosed at first, if it is not treated, it can have disastrous effects on the liver and ultimately affect general health and wellbeing. This may lead to serious liver damage, including hepatocellular carcinoma and liver cirrhosis. This study targets Omani citizens to assess their knowledge, attitudes, and preventive practices regarding HCV.
Significance of the Study	Understanding current awareness levels, beliefs, and behaviors will develop effective educational campaigns and promoting responsible practices to prevent the spread of HCV. The study's findings will contribute significantly to efforts to reduce the burden of HCV infection by promoting knowledge, positive attitudes, and responsible behaviors, in safeguarding the health and well-being of participants at the University of Nizwa.
Aim of the Study	The research aims to identify knowledge gaps, assess attitude, assess current practices, and determine educational needs.
Methodology	The study recruited 100 participants from all 11 governorates in Oman and gather data by using a convenience random sampling technique and excluded the non-Omanis and previously received treatment for the disease. A cross-sectional Descriptive study design was selected. Data statistically assessed using a statistical program (SPSS version 20).
Overall Outcome	The result shows that the research population have good knowledge (74.4%), positive attitude (86.2%) and good practices (70.2%). This study suggests that there are communities. However, the study suggests that better HCV knowledge can lead to good practices.
Keywords	<i>student and staff, Hepatitis C viral infection</i>

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GP Title	PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY AND PREPAREDNESS FOR HOSPITAL PRACTICE AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS
GP Student(s)	Weaam Hamed Al-Busaidi
GP Supervisor(s)	Mr. Phildon Jonar M. Austria
Problem Statement	The development of professional identity and readiness for hospital practice are essential components of nursing education. Lack of clarity regarding one's professional identity can adversely affect nursing students' self-esteem and the value they place on their opinions that affect quality of care they render.
Significance of the Study	Professional identity of nursing students on the aspects of professional values, ethical principles, and commitment to the nursing profession are extremely important. The results can help sustain excellence in nursing education, improve the general level of nursing practice, and better prepare nursing students for their future roles in the clinical setting by making some adjustments in the educational approach and clinical training methods.
Aim of the Study	The study intends to explore the level of professional identity and readiness for clinical practice among undergraduate Nursing students of the University of Nizwa and to explore the correlation between these two variables.
Methodology	Quantitative descriptive correlational design was utilized in the study involving 113 nursing students and were randomly selected. Those who have not yet exposed in the clinical area were excluded. IBM SPSS V.20 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	Majority of nursing students of the Nizwa University are adequately prepared for hospital practice, have sufficient confidence in various nursing procedures, and are prepared to assume future nursing positions. A statistical significant positive correlation were found between professional identity on the following aspects: confidence ($r=0.194$, $p < 0.05$), collaboration ($r=0.295$, $p < 0.01$), management ($r=0.307$, $p < 0.01$), science ($r=0.261$, $p < 0.01$), holistic care ($r=0.219$, $p < 0.05$) and self-directed learning ($r=0.213$, $p < 0.05$) indicating stronger professional identity. Overall, the findings suggest that professional identity plays a significant role in enhancing multiple dimensions of clinical readiness.
Keywords	<i>professional identity, preparedness, hospital practice, nursing students</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	PERCEIVED CHARACTERISTICS OF AN EFFECTIVE CLINICAL INSTRUCTORS BY UON NURSING STUDENTS
GP Student(s)	Asil Said Al Flaiti Safaa Abdulhakeem Al-Bimani
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Leahleonila Tungcul Dr. Oscar Turingan
Problem Statement	Clinical instructors have a significant influence on students' learning because they provide guidance, mentorship, and feedback in addition to creating a conducive learning environment. Their expertise, support, and teaching methods have a big impact on students' development into competent, compassionate nurses. To facilitate the best possible clinical learning, clinical instructors must possess all the attributes of a great teacher, including professionalism, role modeling, clinical proficiency, and communication skills.
Significance of the Study	The study offers important insights that may be applied to enhance clinical teaching techniques by determining the traits and attributes of clinical instructors that nursing students at the University of Nizwa consider to be most influential. Gaining insight into the qualities that students value most in their teachers can assist customize clinical instruction to better fit the needs of students, which will ultimately result in the creation of more capable and self-assured nursing professionals.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to determine the important characteristics of the effective clinical instructor perceived by nursing students at University of Nizwa
Methodology	An exploratory cross-sectional quantitative survey approach was used in this study to find out what nursing students thought were the most beneficial aspects of their clinical instructors that affected their clinical learning experiences. The University of Nizwa hosted the study, which comprised 122 nursing students who had experienced clinical settings at different points in their course. IBM SPSS V.20 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	The findings indicate significant disparities between the perceptions of effective clinical instructor characteristics held by male and female UON nursing students. The most essential quality, according to female students, was "Professional Competence," which indicates the instructor's skill and expertise in clinical practice. Conversely, they gave the lowest rating to "Empathy towards students' challenges," which entails comprehending and recognizing students' struggles. "Energy and Enthusiasm," which reflects the teacher's energy and enthusiasm for instructing, received the highest rating from male pupils.
Keywords	<i>Clinical Instructors, effective clinical instructors, characteristics of an effective clinical instructor</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	THE ATTITUDE AND STIGMA TOWARDS CANCER AND CANCER PATIENTS AMONG STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
Student(s)	Al Rayyan Bati Al Yaqoubi
Supervisor(s)	Ms. Tessy Johny
Problem Statement	Cancer remains a major public health issue in Oman, with rising morbidity and mortality rates and a social stigma. Every year, almost 1,000 people die from cancer. Though public perceptions of cancer have improved, many still believe that cancer is a punishment from God, contagious, or incurable. These myths contribute to negative attitudes and stigma. However, there is also a positive shift, with some people offering support to those affected.
Significance of the Study	Understanding public attitudes and stigma towards cancer in Oman is crucial for healthcare providers to offer culturally sensitive care. It can improve treatment, prevention, patient support, and quality of life, while guiding policy development and resource use. Additionally, it can raise awareness and improve the attitudes of the younger Omani population towards cancer and patients.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to assess the attitude and stigma towards cancer and cancer patients among students at the University of Nizwa and to assess the relationship between attitude to cancer and information needs.
Methodology	A cross-sectional design was used, aiming at 400 students who are currently studying at the University of Nizwa. Exclusion criteria included students less than 18 years of age and have cancer or had a history of cancer. 370 subjects were selected by using convenience sampling. Data was collected via an online survey. SPSS version 21 was used for data analysis
Overall Outcome	The results showed that most participants had positive attitudes toward cancer treatment effectiveness and the ability of patients to recover and contribute to society. Age negatively influenced attitudes, showing fewer positive views, though this relationship was not statistically significant ($p = 0.07$). Most participants did not display significant discomfort (89.73%) or avoidance (90.81%) toward cancer patients. Gender had a significant impact, with women generally holding more negative perceptions of cancer than men ($p < 0.05$). Educational status did not significantly affect attitudes ($p = 0.31$), while attending college, particularly in health sciences, was associated with more positive attitudes ($p < 0.05$).
Keywords	<i>attitude, cancer, cancer patients</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	A STUDY TO ASSESS THE QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG ELDERLY POPULATION IN WADI NAM, OMAN
Student(s)	Bayan Mohammed al-Saadi
Supervisor(s)	Ms. Tessy Johny
Problem Statement	Elderly people are a vulnerable part of society. In Oman, the population aged 60 and above is expected to rise to 13.1% by 2050, up from 6.1% in 2012. This growth will increase the demand for healthcare services, including physical, psychological, and community support, significantly affecting the quality of life of the elderly. As life expectancy increases, improving the quality of life for seniors has become a global priority.
Significance of the Study	Understanding the quality of life of the elderly helps healthcare providers assess their health status and take steps to improve well-being and treatment. It also supports in refining programs for elderly care, ensuring services are high-quality, flexible, and meet the needs of all individuals, regardless of age or health conditions.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to assess the level of quality of life (QoL) among the elderly population in Wadi Nam community in Wilayat Al Qabil and also to examine the association between level of quality of life (QoL) with selected demographic variables.
Methodology	A cross-sectional design was used to target 100 respondents aged 60 or older. Exclusion criteria included individuals under 60, those unable to participate due to chronic mental illnesses or severe cognitive impairment, and those living in remote mountain areas. Purposive sampling selected the 100 respondents, and data were collected using the OPQOL-35 survey. SPSS version 21 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	This study assessed the quality of life (QoL) among elderly individuals, revealing that 40% reported a good quality of life. When asked about life overall, 82% enjoyed their life, 70% were happy much of the time, and 67% looked forward to things. The study analyzed the impact of sociodemographic and lifestyle factors on QoL. The sociodemographic model significantly predicted QoL, explaining 50.7% of the variance ($F(8, 88) = 3.806, R^2 = 0.507$), while the lifestyle factors model explained 53.1% of the variance ($F(7, 91) = 5.100, R^2 = 0.531$). These results highlight the significant influence of both sociodemographic and lifestyle factors on the QoL of elderly individuals.
Keywords	<i>quality of life, elderly</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	IMPACT OF SMARTPHONE USE AT BEDTIME ON SLEEP QUALITY AMONG COLLEGE OF HEALTH SCIENCES STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Sara Abdul Aziz Alwahshi Reem Juma Alamri
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Nawal Al Abri
Problem Statement	The widespread use of smartphones among Health Sciences students at the University of Nizwa (UON), specifically before bedtime for extended periods, raises concerns about its impact on sleep quality. Excessive smartphone use, especially late at night, may disrupt the natural sleep-wake cycle which is defined as a 24-hour daily sleep pattern that should consist of approximately 16 hours of daytime wakefulness and 8 hours of sleeping at nighttime (National Heart, 2022).
Significance of the Study	The findings from this study can guide the development of educational initiatives and awareness campaigns to encourage better sleep hygiene among college students. By highlighting the potential negative effects of smartphone use right before bed on sleep quality, educational institutions like the University of Nizwa can empower students to make informed choices about their technology habits and prioritize their sleep health.
Aim of the Study	To assess the impact of smartphone, use at bedtime on the quality of sleep among College of Health Sciences students at the University of Nizwa.
Methodology	a cross-sectional study using a self-administered questionnaire on the impact of smartphone use on sleeping patterns.it was conducted among 222 Students at the College of Health Sciences from Nizwa University in Al-Dakhiliya Governorate, 140 students from the School of Nursing, 65 from the School of Pharmacy, and 17 from the School of Rehabilitation and Medical Science.
Overall Outcome	Most of the participants (98.6%) used smartphones before sleeping while lying in bed, the majority170 (76.6%) used smartphones every day, 91 (41.0%) had taken more than 1 hour to fall asleep, 50 (%) had taken 1hr. majority 104 (46.8%) have too-bad sleep quality, and 64 (28.8%) have fairly bad sleep quality.
Keywords	<i>smartphone, sleep quality</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS TOWARD THE CARE OF CRITICALLY-ILL CLIENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Ishraq Hamed Salim Alkhatri
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Jiji Joseph
Problem Statement	Critical care units require particular knowledge and skills; thus, nursing students must strengthen their critical thinking skills and grasp of medical concepts. For patient safety and care quality, a positive attitude toward the profession is equally important.
Significance of the Study	By evaluating nursing students' knowledge and attitudes in important areas, this study can help identify the strengths and flaws that can promote the development of targeted treatments and educational activities. Both the quality of patient care and the standards of care provided by prospective nursing professionals could be greatly enhanced by this.
Aim of the Study	The study aimed to assess the knowledge and attitude of undergraduate nursing students toward care of critically-ill clients and to explore the correlation between these two variables.
Methodology	The study employed a cross-sectional correlational design, and a total sampling technique was used to obtain 28 samples. The data was gathered via a self-reported questionnaire, and both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for analysis.
Overall Outcome	Findings revealed that (57.1%) of the students had poor knowledge, while (28.6%) exhibited moderate knowledge, and only (14.3%) demonstrated good knowledge according to Bloom's cutoff values. Furthermore, 68 % of the students were categorized as having a negative attitude toward the care of critically ill patients. The results of a statistical correlation analysis showed a substantial (p-value <0.01) and positive correlation (r = 0.644) between the knowledge and attitude ratings. This suggests that the student's poor knowledge directly contributed to their negative attitude toward the care of critically ill patients. Overall, the results highlight a critical gap in both knowledge and attitude that could impact future nursing practices.
Keywords	<i>knowledge, attitude, critical care areas, nursing students</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	AWARENESS AND USE OF ENERGY DRINKS AMONG STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA, SULTANATE OF OMAN
GP Student(s)	Bayan Suliman Nasser Al-Ishaqi Fasail Saud Alhabsi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Jiji Joseph
Problem Statement	Energy drinks are marketed as mind and body stimulants and contains caffeine, sugar, carbohydrates, and dietary supplements to improve alertness and physical performance. However, there are growing concerns about the safety of these drinks. Major health issues like headaches, anxiety, behavioral issues, and insomnia can arise from overindulging. Ignorance about energy drinks has negative health effects.
Significance of the Study	This study assesses the students' actual energy drink consumption and awareness as well as to make sure they are aware of the harmful health implications linked to excessive consumption. The study's findings are expected to benefit both societies at large and university students in particular.
Aim of the Study	The study aimed to assess the awareness and use of energy drinks among university students.
Methodology	This is a descriptive cross- sectional study involving 100 participants from the university using a simple random sampling. The data were analyzed using descriptive analysis and the Chi-square test of association.
Overall Outcome	The findings showed that 34% of students used energy drinks to increase their focus while studying, even though they were aware of the health risks. Red Bull is the most popular energy drink among students, accounting for 46% of their consumption, followed by Mixa 5G at 4%. Furthermore, 43% of students think they drink coffee. In addition, 7% did not drink energy drinks. 73% of people who did not consume energy drinks, however, claim to have read and heard about the harmful effects of these drinks. Female participation in the study was 84%, significantly higher than male participation at 16%. Additionally, 66% of participants were aged 18-23, while 14% were 30 years and older. There was no association found between the consumption of energy drinks with its selected demographic variables.
Keywords	<i>awareness, energy drinks, university students</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	EXPLORING THE FACTORS INFLUENCING WOMEN'S KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDES TOWARD FAMILY PLANNING IN NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Wajdan Yaqoob AL-Hrrasi Khulood Nassir Al- Maskari
GP Supervisor(s)	Ms. Nawal Al Abri
Problem Statement	This study aims to fill the knowledge gap regarding the factors that influence women's decisions about family planning and birth spacing in Nizwa, Oman. While family planning is acknowledged as a crucial aspect of reproductive health, the specific social, demographic, economic, and cultural factors that shape women's attitudes and practices in this region have been largely underexplored. This lack of insight creates significant challenges for families, caregivers, students, and researchers.
Significance of the Study	The findings from this research will prove invaluable for healthcare providers. By recognizing the specific needs of individuals and couples, providers can tailor family planning programs to enhance awareness, implementation, and promotion effectively. This tailored approach is essential for ensuring that family planning initiatives resonate with the local population, ultimately leading to better health outcomes. Furthermore, the insights gained from this study serve as a resource for family and reproductive health professionals, students, and researchers.
Aim of the Study	To identify the multifaceted factors that may influence women's perspectives on family planning and birth spacing in Nizwa.
Methodology	Quantitative, cross sectional study conducted among 20 women at Farq and Nizwa Health Centers
Overall Outcome	The study identified women's age, duration of marriage, and family income as key factors influencing contraceptive use. Higher contraceptive use was observed among older women, those married for over 15 years, and those with higher household incomes. No significant association was found between women's employment status and contraception use, which contrasts with findings from other regions. While education and husbands' age showed borderline significance, disparities in reproductive health education were evident, indicating the need for improved educational programs.
Keywords	<i>family planning, contraceptive use, reproductive health, women's education, birth spacing, sociodemographic factors</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	IMPACT OF BODY MASS INDEX ON OSTEOARTHRITIS AMONG ADULT OMANI PATIENTS
GP Student(s)	Asara Yousuf Salim Alsaadi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Jestoni Maniago
Problem Statement	Osteoarthritis (OA) is a degenerative joint disease that causes chronic pain and dysfunction, affecting millions globally. The prevalence of OA continues to rise, particularly among individuals with obesity, a common coexisting condition. In Oman, OA remains a significant health concern, but the relationship between body mass index (BMI) and OA prevalence has not been thoroughly explored in the Omani population.
Significance of the Study	The rising prevalence of OA and its association with obesity make it crucial to understand how BMI influences OA in Omani patients. Investigating the impact of BMI on OA prevalence could provide insights into preventive measures, particularly in managing obesity as a modifiable risk factor, which may help improve the quality of life for OA patients and reduce healthcare costs.
Aim of the Study	This study aims to examine the prevalence of osteoarthritis among different BMI categories, explore the factors influencing BMI, and assess how BMI affects Omani patients with OA.
Methodology	A survey study was conducted at Nizwa Hospital, involving 54 adult patients diagnosed with osteoarthritis. Participants were selected using a convenient random sampling technique. Data on demographics, BMI, and the severity of OA were collected and analyzed.
Overall Outcome	The study found that the majority of patients were in the 50-64 age group (53.7%) and were predominantly female (59.3%). Most patients were married (70.4%) with primary education (51.9%) and had a middle-income level (74.1%). The majority (42.6%) of patients were overweight, with the knee being the most commonly affected joint. The results showed no statistically significant difference between OA prevalence and BMI categories ($P > 0.05$). The study highlights the importance of weight management in OA treatment, emphasizing that maintaining a healthy weight could reduce symptom severity and improve functional outcomes.
Keywords	<i>Osteoarthritis, body mass index, adult population, quality of life</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME AWARENESS AMONG FEMALE COLLEGE STUDENTS IN OMAN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY
GP Student(s)	Fatmah Salim Ali Alsubhi Rawia Rabia Amur Al-Maskari
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Jestoni Maniago
Problem Statement	Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a common hormonal disorder that affects women of reproductive age, leading to significant health challenges. These include infertility, gestational diabetes, high blood pressure, heart disease, and mental health issues like depression and higher divorce rates. Despite its prevalence, there is limited awareness among young women, especially in the context of early detection and symptom management.
Significance of the Study	PCOS can significantly impact women's health, and early awareness of the syndrome is crucial for managing symptoms and preventing long-term complications. College students, particularly those of childbearing age, are at a critical point where understanding PCOS can influence early diagnosis and empower them to seek timely interventions. This study contributes to understanding the level of awareness about PCOS among female college students, which could inform future educational efforts aimed at improving women's health outcomes.
Aim of the Study	This study aims to assess the level of awareness about PCOS among female college students at the University of Nizwa and explore factors such as age and academic year that might influence this awareness.
Methodology	A quantitative study design was used, utilizing an online survey to gather data from 293 female students from the College of Health Sciences at the University of Nizwa. The sample was selected using a non-random sampling technique. The survey assessed students' knowledge of PCOS, its symptoms, and potential health consequences.
Overall Outcome	The results indicated a moderate level of awareness of PCOS among the female college students, with 56.5% demonstrating adequate knowledge. The study found that older students and those further along in their academic years had significantly higher levels of awareness. This highlights the importance of providing targeted health education to younger students.
Keywords	<i>PCOS, awareness, female college students, knowledge</i>

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SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	SLEEP QUALITY AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF NURSING STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF NIZWA
GP Student(s)	Zuwaina Khalifa Salim Alanbouri Alia Ali Aljabri
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Jestoni Maniago
Problem Statement	Sleep plays a vital role in overall well-being, impacting cognitive function, psychological health, and academic performance. For nursing students, who often face intense academic pressure and irregular schedules, poor sleep quality can significantly affect their academic success.
Significance of the Study	This study is significant as it highlights how sleep quality can influence academic performance, a critical aspect of nursing education. Furthermore, identifying socio-demographic factors that affect sleep quality can guide interventions to promote better sleep habits and, consequently, improved academic outcomes for nursing students.
Aim of the Study	This study aims to evaluate the relationship between sleep quality and academic performance among nursing students at the University of Nizwa.
Methodology	A cross-sectional study design was used, with 63 nursing students participating through snowball sampling. Data were collected on socio-demographic variables, sleep quality, and academic performance. The study analyzed how factors like academic workload, technology use, and living arrangements influenced sleep quality and academic performance.
Overall Outcome	The study found that the majority of participants were aged 20-24 years (82.54%), predominantly female (92.06%), and mostly single (87.30%). The analysis revealed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.918$, $p = 0.013$) between sleep quality and academic performance. Gender and marital status were also identified as factors influencing sleep quality and academic success. The study underscores the importance of addressing sleep disturbances to enhance students' well-being and academic performance.
Keywords	<i>sleep quality, academic performance, nursing students, socio-demographic variables</i>

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